

WSD/BAROMETRIC TEST BUOYS DEPLOYED IN THE GULF OF MEXICO

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Abstract — Two drifting buoys were configured to accept, process, and transmit barometric pressure signals from three independent low-cost pressure transducers. The "smart barometer" concept is based upon the use of an inexpensive, but stable pressure sensor in conjunction with a microprocessor. The pressure transducers were calibrated to remove their temperature biases with a data correction algorithm, thus establishing the basis for a reliable, accurate, and inexpensive electronic barometer.

INTRODUCTION

Barometers are the most costly meteorological instruments used by the National Data Buoy Center (NDBC). The average cost of a barometer with the accuracy to meet NDBC's requirements is approximately \$2000. As part of an ongoing effort to reduce the cost for barometers and still maintain the long-term accuracy required, a new system package known as the "smart barometer" is being developed. A "smart barometer" system consists of one or more inexpensive, reliable pressure transducers, a microprocessor (or microcontroller), and a temperature sensor.

The pressure transducers selected for evaluation were developed originally for the automotive industry and used in their fuel and pollution control systems. They are reliable and typically cost less than \$100, but are subject to errors in the output signal due to changes in ambient temperature. However, discrepancies between actual and measured pressure values caused by temperature variations are repeatable for a given combination of pressure and temperature. Each transducer was calibrated over the 800 to 1100 hPa pressure range at several temperatures to represent the continuum of the operating range. A set of correction coefficients were then developed using this data.

CONFIGURATION

Two Wind Speed and Direction (WSD) buoys, Argos ID's 7493 and 7494, produced by Polar Research Laboratory (PRL — now Defense Systems, Inc., McLean, Va) were used. These buoys are similar in arrangement to the Tropical Ocean and Global Atmosphere (TOGA) buoys. They are of

the spar design (3.9 x 0.2 m) with a double frustum flotation collar (0.68-m maximum diameter). Modifications were made so that three analog pressure transducers, in addition to the standard barometric sensor, could be installed in each buoy.

The three test pressure transducers in each buoy were labeled as P_A , P_B , and P_C . The models used were the Kavlico Model P312-15A-E1A (0-15 psia) and the SenSym Model SCX15AN (0-15 psia). Buoy 7493 contained the three Kavlico transducers; buoy 7494 contained the three SenSym transducers. A small manifold was constructed for the three test transducers to enable their placement in parallel to the pressure port of the buoy's operational barometer, a Paroscientific model 215-A-073. This Paroscientific barometer, labeled P_S , provided a high-quality ground-truth data reference throughout the experiment. The Argos transmission format was changed to allow all four pressure measurements to be individually transmitted.

Each buoy had attached to it a 2.5-cm-diameter rope drogue with a 29-kg end weight. Buoy 7493 was configured with a 100-m-long drogue and 7494 was configured with a 50-m-long drogue.

METHODOLOGY

The challenge in using this type of "smart" pressure-measuring system was to develop a set of mathematical equations that would correct the measured pressure reading and report an accurate barometric pressure value for any temperature.

Prior to integration into the buoy, each sensor was calibrated using a range of temperatures from -40°C to $+40^{\circ}\text{C}$, and a range of pressures from 800 hPa to 1100 hPa. Characteristic curves were obtained at different individual isothermal conditions, with pressure as the dependent variable and sensor output voltage as the independent variable. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 are typical calibration plots for the Kavlico and for the SenSym barometers. Fig. 1 contains an isothermal calibration line that was done in 1991 and several other isothermal calibration lines done in 1993. The significance of these lines will be discussed later; for now they are presented as an example of the temperature variability and sensitivity of this pressure transducer.

Fig. 1. Isothermal calibration lines for Kavlico transducer no. 2.

Fig. 2. Isothermal calibration lines for Sensym transducer no. 4, conducted in March 1991 and May 1993.

The transducers were calibrated at seven values of applied pressure (with an accuracy of ± 0.1 hPa) at five different temperatures. First, the regression equations were calculated for each of the five isothermal conditions. The coefficients for the y-intercept and for the slope were then used as the basis for two final regression equations. It was then possible to use these last two equations to easily interpolate the sensor temperature and output voltage to arrive at a corrected barometric pressure reading.

Equation (1) was used to represent the transducer's output voltage as a function of the applied pressure and the temperature of the transducer. Each sensor required a specific set of coefficients. As an example, the values of all the coefficients for the interpolation polynomial equation for one of the Sensym transducers are listed below in (1).

$$P = a + bT + cT^2 + (d + eT + fT^2) * (v - g) + 900 \text{ hPa} \quad (1)$$

where:

- P = pressure applied to barometer (hPa),
- T = temperature of barometer ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),
- V = output voltage signal (mv) with an applied gain of 50,
- a = 41.48 (hPa),
- b = 2.682 (hPa/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$),
- c = 0,

- d = 0.3121 (hPa/mv),
- e = 1.018×10^{-3} (hPa/mv per $^{\circ}\text{C}$),
- f = 5.308×10^{-6} (hPa/mv per $^{\circ}\text{C}^2$), and
- g = 3000 mv.

All the particular coefficients for each pressure sensor were entered into the on-board microprocessor. Thus, each "raw" output signal from each sensor is automatically corrected within the processor in real time for both temperature variation and pressure variation, resulting in an accurate barometric pressure reading.

The programming of the NDBC WSD buoy used in this experiment was such that it reported an averaged sample each hour. Each barometric sensor was sampled once every 4 seconds and averaged over an 8-minute period for a total of 120 samples. The barometric data resolution was 0.19 hPa. (The specification has been changed so that the current generation of WSD buoys are taking a 10-minute average.)

PREDEPLOYMENT TESTS

Predeployment testing was conducted during the summer of 1991. Initially, the buoys were placed in a semi-enclosed canal behind NDBC's dock facility. This preliminary testing lasted for 45 days. The buoys were then placed in a large temperature chamber and cycled through a temperature profile from -50°C to $+70^{\circ}\text{C}$ during a period of 24 hours. During all these tests, the measurements reported by all the sensors on the buoy were closely monitored.

It was determined from these tests that the barometric pressure reported from the experimental transducers could be further refined with shore-side postprocessing of each pressure signal by using a linear correction. Since each buoy contained a Paroscientific reference barometer, it was decided that a linear correction would be established using the initial 30-day reporting period after the buoys were actually deployed in the Gulf of Mexico. The results of this can be found in Table 1 and will be discussed later.

Deployment and Data Selection Criteria

The U.S. Coast Guard Cutter *Decisive* on January 19, 1992, deployed the buoys into a gyre that formed in the Gulf of Mexico near 25°N , 93°W . A method was selected to provide a maximum number of data sets per day. The Dispose File from Service Argos was downloaded and sorted to select only the first data transmission from a pass. These were then manually reviewed every few days. The spike-type deviations (obvious errors) in excess of 10 hPa were deleted. An example of such a spike can be seen occurring around September 10 in Fig. 4.

Approximately 2 weeks after the deployment, a controller IC board on buoy 7493 failed, resulting in the loss of data

TABLE 1
SHORESIDE CORRECTION VALUES FOR PRESSURE
READINGS.

	Linear Correction Slope/Y-intercept Values		
	P _A	P _B	P _C
7493:	0.99/2.17	0.98/3.78	1.01/2.44
7494:	1.02/-2.69	0.99/-1.0	10.97/-4.26

Table 1: All values shown in hPa. $P_{corr} = [(P_{i-meas} - 1000 \text{ hPa})/m_i] + b_i + 1000 \text{ hPa}$, where P_{i-meas} is the measured pressure from pressure transducer A, B, or C (corrected for temperature), m_i and b_i are the slope, and y-intercept values are determined from the initial deployment period.

from the reference Paroscientific barometer. However, the data collected prior to this failure was sufficient to establish the shore-side linear correction. Table 1 presents the slope and Y-intercept values used for the linear correction calculations. The electronics associated with the experimental barometric sensors continued to function throughout the remainder of the deployment.

Buoy 7493 Reference Pressure

With the loss of the reference barometer's signal, some criteria had to be established to continue to monitor the performance of the test barometric sensors. It was decided that the average of the three pressure measurements reported from buoy 7493, $(P_A + P_B + P_C)/3$, could be used as the reference value for comparison with each reading. This

provided a basis to determine if individual sensors behaved differently. Normally, the three pressure readings were fairly close to the X-axis (0 hPa), but every few days the signals would expand to ± 1 hPa. This effect can be seen in Fig. 4.

Additionally, the barometric pressure determined by the Paroscientific barometer (P_S) on buoy 7494 was overlaid on to the plot of 7493's Kavlico pressure transducers to determine if there was any drift. During the early months of this experiment, the trends of the pressure matched. In February, when the average separation between the two drifting buoys was 150 km, the average pressure difference between 7493's "reference" value (i.e. $(P_A + P_B + P_C)/3$) and 7494's P_S was -0.33 hPa. In March, the buoy separation was 100 km with an average pressure difference of -0.77 hPa. In April, the separation had increased to 250 and the average difference was +0.56 hPa. Since there seemed little sensor-to-sensor variability on 7493, and the values closely matched the reference value on 7494, this supported the continued use of the average of the three sensors on 7493 as the reference.

Fig. 3 shows a typical time series plot for buoy 7494 from early in the deployment to late in the deployment. Each of the three pressure signals (P_A , P_B , and P_C) are shown. Though it is difficult to read, clearly there was a shift in the calibration of the sensors. On this buoy, pressure error was calculated as the difference between the pressure reported by the reference (Paroscientific) sensor, P_S , and that reported by the individual experimental pressure sensors P_A , P_B , and P_C . Not shown on this figure was a distinct -3 hPa fall observed in the P_C sensor in the latter part of May. The other two transducers have shown a nearly equal amount of drift, but did not show any sudden changes in their reported pressures. When the buoy was recovered in mid-June, the anemometer had been destroyed and the hull was dented. This may have been the result of a collision, and possibly occurred when the P_C sensor showed its sudden shift.

Fig. 4 is a similar time series plot for buoy 7493. As discussed in a previous section, the value of $(P_A + P_B + P_C)/3$

Fig. 3. Time series plot of pressure differences between the reference barometer and each test sensor on buoy 7494 during a) February 1992, and b) June 1992.

was used here as the reference pressure for the "error" calculation. The use of the average of the three sensors most likely is the cause of the repeated short-term jumps in the error values. These occurred throughout the test period, and they typically were observed for only a couple of days. Of major note is the fact that these sensors had to have remained fairly stable in relation to one another; otherwise, the jumps in error would either have been sustained, or increased in value, or both.

GENERAL TRENDS

As a statistical measure of merit, NDBC uses a quality criteria of:

$$Pressure_{err} = \sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon^2} < 1 \text{ hPa}$$

where σ is the standard deviation and ϵ is the standard error based on the differences between the pressure transducers and the reference. Figs. 5 (a) and (b) show this criteria on a monthly basis for each of the buoys.

Fig. 5(a) (buoy 7493) was developed using the mean of P_A , P_B , and P_C as the reference. The buoy has not been recovered to date, so postcalibration has not been possible. The level trend of the plot shows that the Kavlico P312-15A-E1A pressure transducers all have similar drift characteristics. As discussed above, the pressure reading from 7494 was used as a basis to detect any drift in the sensors when the buoys were fairly close together. Based upon this and the "flatness" of the quality criteria lines, it is a very reasonable assumption that this particular pressure transducer has the desired long-term stability characteristics.

Fig. 5(b) (buoy 7494) clearly shows an upward tendency of the monthly values. Additionally, the reading from transducer P_C appears to have drifted at a higher rate. The previously noted 3-hPa fall in late May had some direct impact on this result. As noted before, this may have been the result of a collision. However, it appears that there was

in fact a noticeable drift in the monthly values for all of the sensors.

The belief that the transducers' calibration changed is supported by a comparison between a 1991 calibration curve and a 1993 calibration curve of a fourth transducer (see Fig. 2). The transducer was not deployed on a buoy, but was purchased and calibrated at the same time, using the same excitation voltage for those deployed on buoy 7494. This fourth transducer was not subjected to any major temperature or pressure variations, nor subjected to any shock loads (similar to a collision). Yet the 20 °C line that was measured in 1991 is offset well to the left of the 20°C line measured in 1993. This type of transducer relies upon a substrate to support the actual sensor head; this substrate is constantly undergoing changes as the pressure changes. Based upon this, a piezoresistive-type transducer may not provide the necessary long-term stability for this application.

POSTCALIBRATION OF BUOY 7493

Several attempts have been made to retrieve this buoy from the Gulf of Mexico. A combination of poor weather, schedule conflicts, and the loss of radio signals from the buoy has thwarted our attempts thus far. However, the buoy may have been recovered by a fisherman. In January 1993, the buoy briefly reported via Argos from a location on land near Tampico, Mexico, but thus far the Mexican authorities have not been able to find and return the buoy.

Fig. 6 compares the pressures reported from buoy 7493 and a nearby moored 10-m discus buoy (Station 42002). The plot contains a sample of 88 occurrences where the distance between the two buoys was less than 65 km [Fig. 6(a)]. It can be seen that this sampling spans the majority of the testing period. Fig. 6(b) contains two regression lines. The dashed line represents a linear fit of the data. The heavier dash-dot line represents the residual pressure difference values after adjusting for the distance. This was done by subtracting the value of the regression line from the actual pressure

Fig. 4. Time series plot of pressure error (explained in text) on buoy 7493 during (a) February 1992, and (b) September 1992.

Fig. 5. Quality criteria ($QC = \sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon^2}$). This value should be less than 1 hPa.

Fig. 6. (a) Comparison between barometric pressure readings from station 42002 and drifting buoy 7493. (b) Regression analysis between pressure differences and separation distance.

difference.

The two methods used to compare the pressures reported by buoys 7493 and 7494 (when it was relatively close) with the moored buoy at Station 42002 provides strong encouragement that the Kavlico transducers on-board 7493 had not changed their calibration characteristics during the buoy's deployment. Since there is no substrate base for the sensor to change its stress-strain relationship, and these sensors have demonstrated a suitably long inter-transducer stability (see Fig. 4 and Fig. 5), the capacitive-type transducer was selected as a suitable candidate for additional deployment.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECENT DEVELOPMENTS

The goal of this experiment was to determine if the concept and approach to developing a low-cost alternative barometric pressure sensor was achievable and correct. While it appears that the calibration and modeling of the temperature/pressure characteristics of the pressure transducers did not completely remove all of the detrimental temperature affects over the entire operating temperature range, the output signals from the sensors were repeatable.

What is clearly seen is that each pressure transducer must be proven to have acceptable long-term stability characteristics. Any sensor drift must remain within

calibration limits (i.e., $\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \epsilon^2} < 1$ hPa) for a period of 18 to 24 months.

Currently, four TOGA buoys are each being equipped with two additional capacitive-type pressure transducers. The standard Paroscientific barometer will continue to be used on these four buoys as the reference pressure sensor. The experimental barometric sensors on these four buoys will use a simple dedicated microprocessor and communicate via an RS-232 interface. The same mathematical technique is being used to model the functional relationship between output signal, temperature, and pressure for the individual pressure transducers.

These buoys most likely will be deployed in the South Pacific. The previous deployment of buoys 7493 and 7494 were in the Gulf of Mexico, where environmental conditions tend to be more benign than in the Southern Ocean. Additionally, these U.S. TOGA buoys will not be deployed with drogues. These two factors combined will result in higher buoy motions, thus producing a more rigorous test (in terms of buoy motions) for determining the suitability of these sensors in a buoy environment.

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